

ReViTa Demonstration

This document describes ReViTa’s application regarding the SoS that supports the responses to power outage incidents at the campus of a large Brazilian public university. In the following, we detail the activities of the “SoS Characterization” and “Definition of TACs as a fault tolerance countermeasure” steps.

Step 1. SoS Characterization

Step 1.1. Mission Decomposition: We use mKAOS for mission decomposition. mKAOS is a specific notation for mission specification in SoS. In the mission decomposition, we identify the responsibility of each of the constituent systems. The decomposition diagram is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Mission decomposition.

Step 1.2. Specification of Mission Requirements: The next step involves the specification of mission requirements, which refers to the requirements that constituent systems must fulfill while carrying out their individual missions. These requirements can encompass diverse aspects such as time constraints, performance, and security. A description of the Mission Requirements of the SoS that supports the responses to power outage incidents at the campus of a large Brazilian public university can be found in Table 1. To specify the mission requirements, we use operators from RELAX [1], a language to support the requirements engineering for self-adaptive systems. The RELAX operators are detailed in Figure 2.

Step 1.3. Specification of the states of interest: We define the states of interest of the constituent systems for each mission requirement identified earlier. The state of interest is the state in which a constituent system is able to meet its mission requirements. For the sake of simplicity, we assume that

Table 1: Mission Requirements.

ID	Mission	Mission Requirement
REQ1	Notifying on-call technical team	The notification <i>SHALL</i> be sent <i>AS EARLY AS POSSIBLE</i> after a interruption in the power supply is detected.
REQ2	Notifying on-call technical team	The notification <i>SHALL</i> be sent by telephone call.
REQ3	Notifying on-call technical team	Notifications <i>SHALL</i> be sent at intervals of 30 minutes.
REQ4	Reporting current power consumption	Information about current power consumption <i>SHALL</i> be updated at regular intervals of 30 seconds.
REQ5	Informing battery autonomy	Information about the battery autonomy <i>SHALL</i> be updated at regular intervals of 30 seconds.
REQ6	Informing fuel level	Information about the fuel level <i>SHALL</i> be updated at regular intervals of 30 seconds.
REQ7	Informing local power supply status (active/interrupted)	Information about the local power supply status <i>SHALL</i> be updated at regular intervals of 30 seconds.
REQ8	Informing campus power supply status (active/interrupted)	Information about the power supply at the campus <i>SHALL</i> be updated at regular intervals of 30 seconds.

RELAX operator	Description
Modal Operators	
<i>SHALL</i>	a requirement must hold
<i>MAY . . . OR</i>	a requirement specifies one or more alternatives
Temporal Operators	
<i>EVENTUALLY</i>	a requirement must hold eventually
<i>UNTIL</i>	a requirement must hold until a future position
<i>BEFORE, AFTER</i>	a requirement must hold before or after a particular event
<i>IN</i>	a requirement must hold during a particular time interval
<i>AS EARLY, LATE AS POSSIBLE</i>	a requirement specifies something that should hold as soon as possible or should be delayed as long as possible
<i>AS CLOSE AS POSSIBLE TO [frequency]</i>	a requirement specifies something that happens repeatedly but the frequency may be relaxed
Ordinal Operators	
<i>AS CLOSE AS POSSIBLE TO [quantity]</i>	a requirement specifies a countable quantity but the exact count may be relaxed
<i>AS MANY, FEW AS POSSIBLE</i>	a requirement specifies a countable quantity but the exact count may be relaxed
Uncertainty Factors	
ENV	defines a set of properties that define the system's environment
MON	defines a set of properties that can be monitored by the system
REL	defines the relationship between the ENV and MON properties
DEP	identifies the dependencies between the (relaxed and invariant) requirements

Figure 2: RELAX operators [1].

the fact that the constituent systems are available is sufficient for fulfilling the capabilities requirements defined in the previous activity. Table 2 lists the states of interest associated with mission requirements.

Step 1.4. Specification of observation points: The definition observation points is the last activity of the SoS characterization phase. We defined the “*ping*” (ICMP request and ICMP reply messages) as a observation point to check the availability of the constituent systems. The “*Ping*” package is typically used to verify if the target computer in a network is available.

To monitor the CPU load of the Telephony Gateway, we defined the Simple Network Management Protocol (SNMP) as the observation point. SNMP is a protocol used for monitoring devices connected to a TCP/IP network. Since the Telephony Gateway is a Linux machine, we utilized the Object Identifier

Table 2: States of interest.

ID	Mission Req.	State of interest
SI1	REQ1	Telephony Gateway available
SI2	REQ2	Telephony Gateway available
SI3	REQ3	Telephony Gateway available and with CPU load below 90% .
SI4	REQ4	UPSMS available
SI5	REQ5	UPSMS available
SI6	REQ6	PGMS available and PGMS Fuel Sensors available
SI7	REQ7	PGMS available
SI8	REQ8	PSMS available

(OID) *1.3.6.1.4.1.2021.10.1.3.1* for this purpose.

A specific Application Programming Interface (API) is utilized to verify the Fuel Sensors' availability. When the sensor is unavailable, the API query returns *NULL*.

Step 2. Definition of TAC as a fault tolerance countermeasure

Step 2.1. Specification of mission requirements for TAC: In this activity, non-critical capacity requirements are relaxed to prioritize critical ones. The main idea is that these requirements are considered in the subsequent activity, in which the transient architectural configurations are defined. Table 3 describes the requirements for the TACs, defined in this activity.

Table 3: Mission Requirements for TAC.

ID	Mission	Mission Req.	Mission Req. for TAC
REQ1'	Notifying on-call technical team	The notification <i>SHALL</i> be sent <i>AS EARLY AS POSSIBLE</i> after an interruption in the power supply is detected.	he notification <i>SHALL</i> be sent <i>AS EARLY AS POSSIBLE</i> after a interruption in the power supply is detected. (<i>invariant</i>)
REQ2'	Notifying on-call technical team	The notification <i>SHALL</i> be sent by telephone call.	The notification <i>MAY</i> be sent by telephone call <i>OR</i> SMS <i>OR</i> E-mail.
REQ3'	Notifying on-call technical team	Notifications <i>SHALL</i> be sent at intervals of 30 minutes.	Notifications <i>SHALL</i> be sent at intervals of 30 minutes <i>EVENTUALLY</i> .
REQ4'	Reporting current power consumption	Information about current power consumption <i>SHALL</i> be updated at regular intervals of 30 seconds.	Information about current power consumption <i>SHALL</i> be updated at regular intervals of 30 seconds <i>EVENTUALLY</i> .
REQ5'	Informing battery autonomy	Information about the battery autonomy <i>SHALL</i> be updated at regular intervals of 30 seconds.	Information about the battery autonomy <i>SHALL</i> be updated at regular intervals of 30 seconds <i>EVENTUALLY</i> .
REQ6'	Informing fuel level	Information about the fuel level <i>SHALL</i> be updated at regular intervals of 30 seconds.	Information about the fuel level shall be sent <i>EVENTUALLY</i> .
REQ7'	Informing local power supply status (active/interrupted)	Information about the local power supply status <i>SHALL</i> be updated at regular intervals of 30 seconds.	Information about the local power supply status <i>SHALL</i> be updated at regular intervals of 30 seconds <i>EVENTUALLY</i> .
REQ8'	Informing campus power supply status (active/interrupted)	Information about the power supply at the campus <i>SHALL</i> be updated at regular intervals of 30 seconds.	Information about the power supply at the campus <i>SHALL</i> be sent <i>EVENTUALLY</i> .

Step 2.2. TAC Description: This activity involves considering the previously defined requirements and associating each TAC with one or more violations of states of interest. For the purposes of illustration, a TAC is defined for each problem described in the scenario description and represented using mKAOS notation. Detailed architectural aspects, such as communication interface definitions, are omitted, with the focus solely on the composition of the SoS.

P1 - Telephony Gateway unavailability

The characteristic that represents the state of interest for the Telephony Gateway to fulfill its mission of notifying the on-call technical team is availability. Thus, the unavailability of the Telephony Gateway is a violation of a state of interest and, therefore, should have an associated TAC to address this violation.

For the Telephony Gateway unavailability, we defined a TAC that replaces it with a Mail Server. This does not require replacing other constituent systems and requires the Orchestrator to be able to send messages through the email service. The composition of this TAC would involve a Mail Server, PSMS, PGMS, and UPSMS, as in the Figure 3.

Figure 3: TAC associated to the Telephony Gateway unavailability.

P2 - UPSMS unavailability

Due to the unavailability of the PSMS, it is not possible to determine whether the interruption in the electrical supply is campus-wide or localized. As a result, the decision was made to exclude this information from the notification, as it is not critical for the electrical engineering team to diagnose the issue on-site. The transient architectural configuration for this scenario includes the Telephony Gateway, PGMS, UPSMS, as in Figure 4

P3 - Fuel Level Sensor unavailability

It was decided to exclude the information regarding total autonomy from the notification to address the problem of fuel sensors' unavailability. It is important to mention that the PGMS maintains regular operation even in the unavailability of the fuel sensors. This means detecting an interruption in the electrical energy supply is still possible. Consequently, the transient architectural configuration associated with this problem would involve the constituent systems PGMS, PSMS, and Telephony Gateway, as in Figure 5.

Figure 4: TAC associated to the UPSMS unavailability.

Figure 5: TAC associated to the fuel sensors' unavailability.

References

- [1] J. Whittle, P. Sawyer, N. Bencomo, B. H. C. Cheng, J.-M. Bruel, Relax: A language to address uncertainty in self-adaptive systems requirement, Requirements Engineering 15 (2) (2010) 177–196.